

Supplementary Materials

Bird species identified to the genus-level:

- Large White-headed Gulls (*Larus* sp.), represented by the Lesser Black-backed Gull (*L. fuscus*), and the Yellow-Legged Gull (*L. michahellis*), which can be difficult to distinguish when they are juveniles, and flying at long distances;
- Starlings (*Sturnus* sp.), more specifically during winter, when both the Spotless Starling (*S. unicolor*), and the Common Starling (*S. vulgaris*) are present and can be confounded through vocalization.

Generalized linear mixed models (settings)

We compared taxonomic richness and abundance using generalized linear mixed models (GLMM) with the Poisson error distribution family (Bates et al., 2015). This parametric approach generally provides greater statistical power than a non-parametric approach when its assumptions are met, as is the case in the present analysis. For the taxonomic richness, the GLMM was formulated as follows:

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glmer(richness ~ Type + Season + (1 | Site/Point), family = poisson(link = "log"), [...])
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with “richness” representing the species or family richness (for the bird and arthropod datasets, respectively), “Type” represents the habitat type (i.e., green roofs, grey areas, and urban gardens), “Season” representing the sampling season (Spring vs Winter), and “Site/Point” representing the nested random effect of the site and the sampling point. For the abundance, the GLMM was formulated as follows:

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glmer(abundance ~ Type + Season + (1 | Site/Point) + (1 | Species), family = poisson(link = "log"), [...])
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with “richness” representing the species or family richness (for the bird and arthropod datasets, respectively), “Type” represents the habitat type (i.e., green roofs, grey areas, and urban gardens), “Season” representing the sampling season (Spring vs Winter), “Site/Point” representing the nested random effect of the site and the sampling point, and “Species” (or “Family”, in the case of the arthropods) representing the species (or family) as a crossed random effect.

The GLMM was used to estimate the mean values (and their corresponding 95% confidence intervals) of each habitat type and season. When calculating the model’s estimates, we allowed for the estimation of means and confidence intervals for levels of the random effects not present in the original dataset (`allow.new.levels = TRUE`). Model comparisons were based on the overlap of these 95% confidence intervals. When confidence intervals overlapped, differences were considered not statistically significant ($\alpha = 0.05$). Framing GLM results in terms of confidence intervals rather than relying solely on model summaries improves interpretability by emphasizing the estimated means and their uncertainty, allowing model differences to be evaluated more transparently.

Non-metric Multidimensional Scaling Ordination (settings)

Community composition was explored using non-metric multidimensional scaling (NMDS) separately for birds and arthropods. Prior to ordination, abundance data were Hellinger-standardized to reduce the influence of highly abundant taxa and to make the data more suitable for distance-based multivariate analyses. Hellinger transformation is particularly important in this context because it preserves Euclidean distances among sites while down-weighting rare or highly abundant taxa, which improves the performance and interpretability of ordination techniques such as NMDS (Legendre & Gallagher, 2001).

NMDS was conducted using the *vegan::metaMDS* R-function (Oksanen et al., 2025), specifying a three-dimensional solution ($k = 3$). Automatic data transformation was disabled to prevent additional transformations within the function, as the community matrices had already been Hellinger-transformed prior to distance calculation. To improve convergence and avoid local minima, the ordination was fitted using 50 random starts, with a maximum of 500 tries and 1000 iterations.

For both the arthropod and bird dataset, taxa filtering was applied prior to the NMDS analysis to ensure that the Bray-Curtis dissimilarity matrices could be calculated (i.e., sites with zero occurrences were excluded). However, arthropod families with very low occurrence (i.e., present in two or fewer samples) were also excluded because their inclusion resulted in artificially low stress values, likely driven by data sparsity rather than ecologically meaningful structure. This filtering step improved the robustness and interpretability of the ordination while preserving the main patterns of community composition.

The final NMDS solutions for both birds and arthropods showed stress values of approximately 0.10, which are generally considered to indicate a good representation of the multivariate relationships in reduced ordination space and an acceptable level of distortion for ecological community data (Kruskal, 1964; Clarke, 1993; McCune & Grace, 2002).

Fig. S1 – Map with an example of a set of green roof and respective controls, in Belém, Lisbon: a) Centro Cultural de Belém (green roofs, in yellow); b) Jardim da Praça do Império (urban garden, in blue), and c) Museu da Marinha (grey area, in red) (map created using the Free and Open Source QGIS).

Table S1 – Sampled sites – location, type of site (Green roof, Urban Garden and Grey Area), coordinates (in decimal degrees), and number of bird point counts and arthropod transects done at each site.

LOCATION	TYPE OF SITE	COORDINATES	Point Counts	Transects
Av. E.U.A.	Green Roof	38.749722, -9.139943	1	2
Av. E.U.A.	Urban Garden	38.749559, -9.138187	1	2
Av. E.U.A.	Grey Area	38.748733, -9.138259	1	2
Jardim Ruy Jervis d’Athouguia	Green Roof	38.746232, -9.136139	1	2
Rua Pedro Ivo	Urban Garden	38.746293, -9.137475	1	2
Largo Machado de Assis	Grey Area	38.747241, -9.139479	1	2
Jardim Amália Rodrigues	Green Roof	38.730211, -9.156724	1	2
Jardim Amália Rodrigues	Urban Garden	38.731221, -9.154363	2	2
Palácio de Justiça	Grey Area	38.731677, -9.156862	2	2
Jardins do Palácio Sottomayor	Green Roof	38.728365, -9.147491	1	2
Parque Eduardo VII	Urban Garden	38.728601, -9.150775	1	1
Largo de Andaluz	Grey Area	38.727717, -9.147839	1	1
Rua João Chagas (1)	Green Roof	38.748180, -9.176465	1	2
Rua Cidade de Rabat	Urban Garden	38.747929, -9.179033	1	2
Rua Abílio Mendes	Grey Area	38.748628, -9.179436	1	2

Alameda D. Afonso Henriques	Green Roof	38.737103, -9.132837	1	2
Jardim da Fonte Luminosa	Urban Garden	38.737346, -9.129733	1	2
Entrada Instituto Superior Técnico	Grey Area	38.736890, -9.137023	1	2
Campus de Justiça	Green Roof	38.773257, -9.096279	3	3
Av. Boa Esperança	Urban Garden	38.775171, -9.093774	1	2
ESEL Parking Área	Grey Area	38.777209, -9.098516	1	3
Centro Cultural de Belém	Green Roof	38.695217, -9.209164	2	4
Praça do Império	Urban Garden	38.695575, -9.206368	1	2
Entrada Museu da Marinha	Grey Area	38.697419, -9.208631	1	3
Junta de Freguesia Parque das Nações	Green Roof	38.762247, -9.096887	1	1
Jardim Cabeço das Rolas	Urban Garden	38.760648, -9.097311	1	2
Rua Pedro e Inês	Grey Area	38.760693, -9.094361	1	1
Doca da Ribeira das Naus	Green Roof	38.706473, -9.139452	1	2
Largo do Corpo Santo	Urban Garden	38.706317, -9.142224	1	1
Praça do Município	Grey Area	38.707974, -9.139240	1	1
Azinhaga das Galhardas	Green Roof	38.758514, -9.168031	1	1
Jardim da Av. Ventura Terra	Urban Garden	38.758684, -9.166408	1	1

Escola Alemã de Lisboa – parking area	Grey Area	38.759149, -9.163569	1	1
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Table S2 – List of all bird species recorded during the two sampling periods (winter and spring) in the 19 studied green roofs. Scientific names, common names in Portuguese and English, and abbreviation of the scientific names, used later on in this work in the NMDS analysis. Non-native species are denoted with an asterisk (*).

SCIENTIFIC NAME	PORTUGUESE COMMON NAME	ENGLISH COMMON NAMES
<i>Acridotheres cristatellus</i> *	Mainá-de-crista	Crested Myna
<i>Alisterus scapularis</i> *	Periquito-rei-australiano	Australian King Parrot
<i>Alopochen aegyptica</i> *	Ganso-do-Egipto	Egyptian Goose
<i>Anas platyrhynchos</i>	Pato-real	Mallard
<i>Anthus pratensis</i>	Petinha-dos-prados	Meadow Pipit
<i>Apus</i>	Andorinhões	Typical Swifts
<i>Apus apus</i>	Andorinhão-preto	Common Swift
<i>Apus pallidus</i>	Andorinhão-real	Pallid Swift
<i>Buteo buteo</i>	Águia-d'asa-redonda	Common Buzzard
<i>Cairina moschata</i> *	Pato-mudo	Muscovy Duck
<i>Carduelis carduelis</i>	Pintassilgo	European Goldfinch
<i>Cecropis daurica</i>	Andorinha-dáurica	Red-rumped Swallow
<i>Certhia brachydactyla</i>	Trepadeira-comum	Short-toed Treecreeper
<i>Cettia cetti</i>	Rouxinol-bravo	Cetti's Warbler
<i>Chloris chloris</i>	Verdilhão	European Greenfinch
<i>Chroicocephalus ridibundus</i>	Guincho-comum	Black-headed Gull
<i>Cisticola juncidis</i>	Fuinha-dos-juncos	Zitting Cisticola
<i>Columba livia</i> (var. <i>domestica</i>)	Pombo-doméstico	Domestic Pigeon
<i>Columba palumbus</i>	Pombo-torcaz	Common Wood Pigeon
<i>Corvus corone</i>	Gralha-preta	Carrion Crow
<i>Curruca melanocephala</i>	Toutinegra-dos-valados	Sardinian Warbler
<i>Cyanistes caeruleus</i>	Chapim-azul	Eurasian Blue Tit
<i>Delichon urbicum</i>	Andorinha-dos-beirais	Common House-Martin
<i>Emberiza cia</i>	Cia	Rock Bunting
<i>Erithacus rubecula</i>	Pisco-de-peito-ruivo	European Robin
<i>Estrilda astrild</i> *	Bico-de-lacre	Common Waxbill
<i>Fringilla coelebs</i>	Tentilhão-comum	Common Chaffinch
<i>Gallinula chloropus</i>	Galinha-de-água	Common Moorhen
<i>Garrulus glandarius</i>	Gaio	Eurasian Jay
<i>Hirundo rustica</i>	Andorinha-das-chaminés	Barn Swallow
<i>Larus sp.</i>	Gaivotas	Large White-headed Gulls
<i>Larus fuscus</i>	Gaivota-d'asa-escura	Lesser Black-backed Gull
<i>Larus michahellis</i>	Gaivota-de-patas-amarelas	Yellow-legged Gull
<i>Linaria cannabina</i>	Pintarroxo	Common Linnet
<i>Motacilla alba</i>	Alvéola-branca	White Wagtail
<i>Parus major</i>	Chapim-real	Great Tit
<i>Passer domesticus</i>	Pardal-doméstico	House Sparrow
<i>Periparus ater</i>	Chapim-carvoeiro	Coal Tit
<i>Phalacrocorax carbo</i>	Corvo-marinho	Great Cormorant
<i>Phoenicurus ochruros</i>	Rabirruivo-preto	Black Redstart
<i>Phylloscopus collybita</i>	Felosinha	Common Chiffchaff
<i>Psittacula krameri</i> *	Periquito-rabijunco	Rose-ringed Parakeet
<i>Ptyonoprogne rupestris</i>	Andorinha-das-rochas	Eurasian Crag Martin
<i>Regulus ignicapilla</i>	Estrelinha-real	Common Firecrest

SCIENTIFIC NAME	PORTUGUESE COMMON NAME	ENGLISH COMMON NAME
<i>Serinus serinus</i>	Milheirinha	European Serin
<i>Spinus spinus</i>	Lugre	Eurasian Siskin
<i>Streptopelia decaocto</i>	Rola-turca	Eurasian Collared Dove
<i>Sturnus</i>	Estorninhos	Starlings
<i>Sturnus unicolor</i>	Estorninho-preto	Spotless Starling
<i>Sturnus vulgaris</i>	Estorninho-malhado	Common Starling
<i>Sylvia atricapilla</i>	Toutinegra-de-barrete	Eurasian Blackcap
<i>Thectocercus acuticaudatus</i> *	Periquitão	Blue-crowned Parakeet
<i>Troglodytes troglodytes</i>	Carriça	Eurasian Wren
<i>Turdus philomelos</i>	Tordo-pinto	Song Thrush
<i>Turdus merula</i>	Melro	Common Blackbird

Table S3 – List of all identified arthropod families, and their respective orders and classes, recorded during the two sampling periods (winter and spring) in the 19 studied green roofs.~

CLASS	ORDER	FAMILY
ARACHNIDA	Araneae	Araneidae
		Gnaphosidae
		Linyphiidae
Araneae	Trombidiformes	Salticidae
		Thomisidae
DIPLOPODA	Julida	Erythraeidae
INSECTA	Coleoptera	Julidae
		Carabidae
		Chrysomelidae
		Coccinellidae
		Curculionidae
		Melyridae
		Oedemeridae
		Scarabaeidae
		Scraptiidae
	Staphylinidae	
	Tenebrionidae	
	Diptera	Agromyzidae
		Anthomyiidae
		Apidae
		Calliphoridae
		Cecidomyiidae
		Ceratopogonidae
		Chironomidae
		Chloropidae
		Culicidae
		Dolichopodidae
		Drosophilidae
		Ephydriidae
		Fannidae
		Heleomyzidae
		Hybotidae
		Lauxaniidae
Lonchopteridae		
Muscidae		
Phoridae		
Platystomatidae		
Polleniidae		
Psychodidae		
Rhiniidae		
Rhinophoridae		
Sarcophagidae		

CLASS	ORDER	FAMILY
INSECTA	Diptera	Sciaridae
		Sepsidae
		Simuliidae
		Sphaeroceridae
		Stratiomyidae
		Syrphidae
		Tachinidae
		Tephritidae
	Tipulidae	
	Hemiptera	Aphididae
		Cicadellidae
		Delphacidae
		Lygaeidae
		Miridae
Monophlebidae		
Nabidae		
Pentatomidae		
Pyrrhocoridae		
Hymenoptera	Apidae	
	Braconidae	
	Ceraphronidae	
	Crabronidae	
	Formicidae	
	Halictidae	
	Ichneumonidae	
	Megachilidae	
	Scelionidae	
	Vespidae	
Lepidoptera	Crambidae	
	Noctuidae	
	Nymphalidae	
	Pieridae	
Odonata	Libellulidae	
Thysanoptera	Phlaeothripidae	
MALACOSTRACA	Isopoda	Armadillidiidae

Table S4 – Average abundance (mean number of individuals/point count) of each recorded bird species, on the three types of studied habitats (Green Roofs, Urban Gardens and Grey Areas), in winter and spring. Non-native species are denoted with an asterisk (*). The three highest abundance values in each type of habitat and each season are underlined.

Species	Winter			Spring		
	Green Roofs	Urban Gardens	Grey Areas	Green Roofs	Urban Gardens	Grey Areas
<i>Acridotheres cristatellus</i> *	0.29	0.08	--	--	0.75	--
<i>Anas platyrhynchos</i>	0.21	0.25	--	0.71	0.17	--
<i>Anthus pratensis</i>	--	0.17	--	--	--	--
<i>Cairina moschata</i> *	--	0.42	--	--	0.50	--
<i>Carduelis carduelis</i>	0.07	0.17	0.08	0.07	0.08	--
<i>Certhia brachydactyla</i>	0.14	0.17	--	0.07	0.17	--
<i>Chloris chloris</i>	--	--	--	0.14	0.50	--
<i>Cisticola juncidis</i>	0.07	--	--	--	0.08	--
<i>Columba livia</i>	<u>1.36</u>	<u>2.25</u>	<u>1.08</u>	<u>4.36</u>	<u>4.17</u>	<u>1.08</u>
<i>Columba palumbus</i>	0.07	0.25	--	0.29	0.58	--
<i>Corvus corone</i>	0.07	--	--	--	--	--
<i>Curruca melanocephala</i>	0.21	0.33	--	0.43	0.08	--
<i>Cyanistes caeruleus</i>	0.21	0.50	--	0.14	0.08	--
<i>Delichon urbicum</i>	--	--	--	0.07	0.17	--
<i>Erithacus rubecula</i>	0.21	0.67	--	--	0.08	--
<i>Estrilda astrild</i> *	--	0.75	--	--	--	--
<i>Fringilla coelebs</i>	--	0.08	--	--	--	--
<i>Hirundo rustica</i>	--	--	--	0.07	0.17	--
<i>Larus sp.</i>	0.29	--	<u>1.00</u>	0.07	--	--
<i>Linaria cannabina</i>	--	--	--	0.07	--	--
<i>Motacilla alba</i>	0.29	0.75	<u>0.33</u>	0.43	0.92	--
<i>Parus major</i>	0.07	0.25	--	--	--	--
<i>Passer domesticus</i>	<u>1.14</u>	<u>2.17</u>	<u>0.33</u>	<u>2.14</u>	<u>1.83</u>	<u>0.33</u>
<i>Periparus ater</i>	0.07	0.08	--	--	--	--
<i>Phoenicurus ochruros</i>	0.50	0.08	<u>0.33</u>	0.64	0.25	--
<i>Phylloscopus collybita</i>	0.50	0.58	0.17	--	--	--
<i>Psittacula kramera</i> *	--	0.08	--	--	--	--
<i>Ptyonoprogne rupestris</i>	--	--	--	--	0.08	--
<i>Regullus ignicapilla</i>	--	--	--	--	0.08	--
<i>Serinus serinus</i>	0.21	0.17	--	0.93	0.67	--
<i>Spinus spinus</i>	0.07	--	--	--	--	--
<i>Streptopelia decaocto</i>	--	0.17	--	--	0.50	--
<i>Sturnus sp.</i>	0.21	0.50	--	0.36	1.00	0.17
<i>Sylvia atricapilla</i>	0.36	0.17	--	--	0.33	--
<i>Thectocercus acuticaudatus</i> *	--	0.08	--	--	--	--
<i>Turdus merula</i>	<u>1.00</u>	<u>2.25</u>	<u>0.33</u>	<u>1.79</u>	<u>3.50</u>	<u>0.42</u>

Table S5 – Average abundance, by transect, of each identified arthropod family, on the three types of studied habitats (green roofs, urban gardens and grey areas), in winter and spring. The three highest abundance values in each type of habitat and each season are underlined.

Families	Winter			Spring		
	Green Roofs	Urban Gardens	Grey Areas	Green Roofs	Urban Gardens	Grey Areas
Agromyzidae	--	--	--	0.91	0.26	--
Anthomyiidae	0.04	0.05	--	0.26	0.42	--
Aphididae	0.04	--	--	0.78	<u>20.95</u>	<u>1.10</u>
Apidae	0.39	0.05	0.10	<u>1.52</u>	0.74	0.05
Araneidae	--	--	--	--	0.05	--
Armadillidiidae	--	--	0.05	0.17	0.42	--
Braconidae	--	--	--	0.09	0.11	0.05
Calliphoridae	0.26	<u>0.47</u>	0.10	0.22	2.37	--
Carabidae	--	--	--	0.04	--	--
Cecidomyiidae	--	--	--	0.17	--	0.05
Ceraphronidae	--	--	--	--	0.05	--
Ceratopogonidae	--	0.05	--	0.22	0.32	0.10
Chironomidae	<u>5.26</u>	<u>4.11</u>	<u>1.05</u>	0.87	<u>4.74</u>	0.10
Chloropidae	--	0.32	--	0.04	0.68	--
Chrysomelidae	0.70	--	--	0.30	0.16	--
Cicadellidae	--	0.05	--	0.09	--	0.05
Coccinellidae	--	--	--	0.13	0.42	--
Crambidae	--	--	--	--	0.05	--
Culicidae	--	0.05	--	--	--	--
Curculionidae	--	--	--	0.04	--	--
Delphacidae	--	--	--	0.04	0.05	--
Dolichopodidae	--	--	--	0.04	0.11	--
Drosophilidae	0.09	0.26	--	0.17	--	--
Ephydriidae	<u>1.13</u>	--	--	<u>1.22</u>	0.42	--
Erythraeidae	--	--	--	0.48	--	<u>25.00</u>
Fannidae	--	--	--	--	0.26	--
Formicidae	0.17	<u>6.26</u>	<u>0.55</u>	<u>14.04</u>	<u>69.21</u>	<u>13.95</u>
Gnaphosidae	--	--	--	--	0.16	--
Halictidae	--	--	--	--	0.11	--
Heleomyzidae	--	--	--	0.04	0.21	--
Hybotidae	--	--	--	0.04	--	--
Ichneumonidae	--	0.05	--	0.09	0.21	0.05
Julidae	--	--	--	--	--	0.05
Lauxaniidae	--	--	--	0.04	--	--
Libellulidae	--	--	--	0.09	0.05	--
Linyphiidae	--	--	--	--	0.16	0.10
Lonchopteridae	--	--	--	0.13	0.05	--
Lygaeidae	--	0.05	--	--	--	--
Melyridae	--	--	--	--	0.05	--
Miridae	--	--	--	--	0.16	--
Monophlebidae	0.04	--	--	--	--	--

Families	Winter			Spring		
	Green Roofs	Urban Gardens	Grey Areas	Green Roofs	Urban Gardens	Grey Areas
Muscidae	<u>0.87</u>	0.11	<u>0.50</u>	0.70	0.53	--
Nymphalidae	0.13	--	--	0.22	0.42	0.05
Oedemeridae	--	--	--	0.04	--	--
Phoridae	--	0.05	--	0.26	0.11	--
Pieridae	0.04	0.05	0.05	0.13	0.37	0.05
Platystomatidae	--	--	--	0.04	0.11	--
Polleniidae	--	0.21	--	--	--	--
Psychodidae	--	--	--	0.04	--	--
Rhiniidae	--	0.05	--	--	--	--
Rhinophoridae	--	--	--	0.04	--	0.10
Salticidae	--	0.05	--	--	0.11	--
Sarcophagidae	0.13	--	--	0.13	0.58	--
Sciaridae	0.52	--	--	--	0.05	--
Scraptiidae	--	--	--	--	--	0.10
Sepsidae	--	--	0.05	--	0.11	--
Sphaeroceridae	--	--	--	0.96	0.11	--
Staphylinidae	0.30	--	--	--	0.05	--
Stratiomyidae	--	--	--	--	0.05	--
Syrphidae	0.17	0.11	0.30	0.70	1.26	0.05
Tenebrionidae	--	--	--	--	--	0.05
Tephritidae	0.43	--	<u>0.50</u>	--	--	--
Tipulidae	0.09	0.16	--	--	0.11	--
Vespidae	0.13	0.05	--	0.39	0.37	--

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